

Reduction of Briquetting Waste Fine El-Dekhila Iron Ore Pellets (Egypt)

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Abstract— In the present work, an attempt has been made to study the reduction behavior and kinetics of briquette waste fired El-Dekhila iron ore briquette. The effect of different reduction parameters such as temperature and hydrogen flow rate also, the effect of drop damage resistance, applied pressure and compressive strength was studied. Reduction of briquetting fine waste El-Dekhila pellets by hydrogen is carried out in the temperature range 700 to 1000 °C. In the reduction kinetic study, the most satisfactory model is to take the slope of the initial linear region of fractional reduction vs. time curve as a measure of rate constant (k) and ln k vs. 1/T plots are straight line from which activation energy was calculated. In kinetic studies relating to reduction of ores, a mechanism is assumed that correlates time (t) to conversion (R): $R=F(t)$

The most satisfactory model is that which gives the higher R² coefficient on plotting F (R) against (t).

Keywords— Fired briquetting waste El-Dekhila fine pellets, reduction kinetics, diffusion model, energy of activation.

I. INTRODUCTION

In the nature, pure iron is not found because it has a high tendency to oxygen. In general, iron is found as iron oxide with other materials like: silicon, sulfur, phosphorus and manganese. Iron oxide with all other materials which exists in the nature calls iron ore or iron stone and is usually found in the form of magnetite (Fe₃O₄), hematite (Fe₂O₃), goethite (FeO(OH)), limonite (FeO(OH).n(H₂O)), siderite (FeCO₃) and Pyrite (FeS₂) [Ashrafian et al., (2011)].

Iron oxides may exist in hematite (Fe₂O₃), magnetite (Fe₃O₄) and wüstite (FeO) depending on temperature and oxygen potential of the system. Although the non-stoichiometric wüstite is usually written as FeO or Fe_xO, the value of x in Fe_xO is less than unity and close to 0.95 when it co-exists with metallic iron.

Iron cation exists as two different valences (Fe²⁺, Fe³⁺) in oxides forming three different iron oxides, i.e. hematite, magnetite and wüstite in descending order of oxidation. In addition to hematite, Fe₂O₃ has also another crystalline form called maghemite (γ-Fe₂O₃), but that form is very unstable [Hughes et al., (1982)].

More than 90% of iron is produced in the blast furnace process while the balance is produced by the direct reduction processes [Yearbook and Association, (2010)].

The briquetting process is an agglomeration process of ores in which lumps are formed by compacting the iron bearing fines and dust with addition of binder and also de-airing these mixtures inside the vacuum chamber of the briquetting machine. This process aims at recycling and reusing of the low-grade iron ore and plant fines. This product can be used as a feed in blast furnace operation [Belkin et al., (2003)].

II. EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURES

2-1. Raw Material

El-Dekhila waste pellets which used in this work were delivered from El-Dekhila steel Company (Alexandria, Egypt). The chemical analyses of this fine are Fe total = 66.5%, Fe₂O₃ = 95%, SiO₂ = 1.5% and CaO = 0.7%.

The X-ray of El-Dekhila pellets waste was illustrated in (Fig. 1) from which it is clear that the main compound of this waste is hematite.

Fig. 1. X-ray of El-Dekhila pellets waste.

2.2. Preparation of Samples in the Form of Briquettes

Preparation of samples for the briquetting process was carried out by mixing 10g of El-Dekhila fine with 2% molasses (binding material) was pressed in the mould (12mm

diameter and 22 mm height) using MEGA.KSC-10 hydraulic press [Inass, (2016)] (Fig. 2).

Fig. 2. MEGA.KSC-10 hydraulic press.

Determination of the quality of the produced briquettes

a. Drop damage resistance test

The produced briquettes were subjected to mechanical tests (Drop damage resistance test). The drop damage resistance indicates how often briquette can be dropped from a height of 45 cm before they show perceptible cracks or crumbed.

Ten briquettes are individually dropped on a steel plate until their breaking. The mean value of the tested briquettes gives their average drop number [Mayer, (1980), Forsmo et al., (2006) and Forsmo et al., (2008)].

b. Compressive strength test

The average compressive strength test of briquette [Annual book of ASTM (2012)] is controlled by compressing at least 10 of briquettes between parallel steel plates up their breaking. The mean value of the tested briquettes gives their compressive strength.

2.3. Reduction Procedure by Hydrogen

The reduction of briquette by hydrogen was done in the thermo gravimetric apparatus (schematic diagram of thermo gravimetric apparatus [Inass, (2016)] is shown in (Fig. 3) It consists of vertical furnace, electronic balance for monitoring the weight change of reacting sample and temperature controller. The sample was placed in a Ni-Cr crucible which was suspended under the electronic balance by Ni-Cr wire. The furnace temperature was raised to the required temperature (700-1000 °C) and maintained constant to ± 5 °C. Then the sample was placed in the hot zone. The nitrogen flow rate was 0.5l/min in all experiments at initial time to the end of reduction. The weight of the sample was continuously recorded, at the end of the run; the samples were withdrawn from the furnace and kept in the desiccators.

The percentage of reduction was calculated according to the following equation:-

$$\text{Reduction percentage} = \frac{(W_0 - W_t) * 100}{\text{Oxygen (mass)}} = \%$$

Where:-

W_0 the initial mass of iron ore sample after removal of moisture, g.

W_t : mass of sample after each time, t, g

Oxygen (mass): indicates the mass of oxygen percent in Fe_2O_3 .

Fig. 3. Schematic diagram of thermo balance apparatus.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Effect of Forming Pressure on Drop Damage Resistance

(Fig. 4) illustrates the effect of forming pressure on the drop damage resistance of green briquette which pressed at constant binding materials percent 2% molasses at the same day of formation and after 3 days of formation, from this figure it is clear that as the forming load increased the drop number of green briquette at the same day of formation and after 3 days of formation increased. This could be attributed to the fact that increasing forming load leads to increase the number of contact points between particles and subsequently the Vander Waals force increased [Ingles, (1962), Mohamed et al., (2004) and Mangena and Cann., (2007)].

Fig. 4. Drop damage resistance and forming pressure (MPa).

Effect of Forming Pressure on the Strength of the Briquette

(Fig. 5) illustrates the relation between the forming pressure and strength of the green briquette formed at the same day and after 3 days of formation, from which it is clear that as the forming pressure increases, the strength increases.

Fig. 5. The relation between the forming pressure and strength of the green briquette formed at the same day and after 3 days of formation.

Relation between Forming Pressure and Compressive Strength at Different Temperature of Firing

(Fig. 6) illustrates the relation between forming pressure and compressive strength at different temperature of firing, from which it is clear that as the firing temperature increases, the strength of the briquette increases. This may be due to the increase of bonding force between atoms due to the increase of attraction between them.

Effect of the Forming Pressure on the Reduction Percentage

(Fig. 7) shows the relation between the forming pressure and reduction percentage, from this figure it is clear that as the forming pressure increased, the reduction percentage decreased.

Fig. 6. The Relation between compressive strength and forming pressure at different temperature of firing.

Fig. 7. Reduction percentage at 86.7, 130.05, 173.4, 216.75, 260.1MPa.

This may be due to the decrease of the space between atoms (i.e. porosity decreases and so the contact between particles and the reducing gas decreases too). This is in accordance with [Awad S. S., (2017)].

Reduction Percentage at Different Hydrogen Flow Rate

(Fig. 8) illustrates the relation between the reduction percentage and hydrogen flow rate at temperature 900 °C (compressive strength 173.4 MPa) from which it is clear that as hydrogen flow rate increased, the reduction percentage increased.

Fig. 8. Reduction percentage at 0.5, 1, 1.5, 2 liter hydrogen (temperature 900 °C)

This may be due to the increase of flow rate leads to an increase of number of hydrogen moles in the bulk phase which in turn leads to the raise of hydrogen adsorption and subsequently the rate of reaction increased [Shalabi, (1973)], or the increase of flow rate increased the gas diffusion across the boundary layer subsequently the reduced ion increased [Sayed et al., (2002)]. Also, may be due to the higher flow rate prevailing in the reaction zone which enhances the rate of hydrogen adsorption and subsequently the rate of chemical reaction steps increased [Sayed et al., (2001)].

Fig. 9. Reduction percentage at 700, 800, 900, 1000 °C at hydrogen flow rate =1.5 l/min.

Reduction Percentage at Different Reduction Temperatures

The reduction was carried out at different temperatures ranging from 700°C to 1000°C, where the weight of the briquette was constant and the hydrogen flow rate =1.5 l/min.

The results of the investigation are shown in (Fig. 9) for the briquette. It is clear that the increase of temperature favors the reduction rate and degree. The analyses of the curve relating the reduction percentage and time of reduction, shows that each curve has 3 different values of reduction rates. The first value is high while the second is somewhat slower and the third is the slowest one.

Kinetics Reduction of the Briquette of El-Dekhaila Waste Pellets

Kinetic studies for estimation the apparent activation energies were carried out for the pellets at different temperatures ranging from 700 °C up to 1000 °C for different time intervals in the range of 0-60 min.

a) Reaction model

When the reaction model was assumed, a plot of $1 - (1-R)^{1/3}$ against time produced straight lines of high values of R^2 (Fig. 10).

Fig. 10. The relationship between $1 - (1-R)^{1/3}$ Versus reduction time at 700, 800, 900, 1000 °C.

Fig. 11. The Arrhenius plot for the reduction process of briquette.

This was used to calculate the values of the reaction rate constant (k) in the equation:

$$kt = 1 - (1 - R)^{1/3}$$

TABLE 1. shows the values of k at different temperatures.

Temperature	700 °C	800 °C	900 °C	1000 °C
k (min ⁻¹)	0.0216	0.0219	0.0368	0.0492

When ln k was plotted against 1/T (Fig. 11), the activation energy of the reduction reaction was calculated and equal to 30.08kJ/mol.

IV. CONCLUSION

1. Increase forming pressure leads to increase the drop damage resistance (drop number of pellet).
2. Compressive strength of fired El-Dekhaila Pellets waste fine increased as the temperature of firing increased.
3. An increase of reduction temperature increased the rate of reduction.
4. The activation energies calculated for this process for El-Dekhaila Pellets waste fine formed using equation $kt = 1 - (1 - R)^{1/3}$ was = 30.080 kJ/mol.

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